

Diving Deep into MQTT: Unveiling Attack Patterns Through Clustering of Traffic Flows

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Abstract—Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) is considered the most significant protocol for IoT, standing out for its lightweight and high functionality in unreliable, limited resources networks. In this work, we analyze MQTT behavior using a collection of 211M benign and malicious packets from 6 datasets. Using 3 traffic flow generation tools to generate flows, we perform K-means clustering on the flows of each individual dataset to understand the traffic’s underlying behavior. Our results show that in 65% of the cases, the optimum number of clusters is 2. With only 1 dataset having two different classes and the other 5 having 4 or more, indicating high similarity between the samples from the different classes and difficulty in drawing clear boundaries between the traffic types. Further analysis using feature ranking shows that a single feature (Flow Duration) weighs on average 70-90%, thus reducing other features’ impact.

Index Terms—Traffic, Flow, Clustering, K-means, Zeek, MQTT, malicious, Argus, attack

I. INTRODUCTION

IoT adoption is on the rise. Active IoT devices are estimated to be over 20B by the end of 2025 and are expected to double by 2033 [1]. One of the leading IoT protocols is MQTT, standing out for its lightweight publish/subscribe nature and efficient operability in low-bandwidth environments [2]. Through MQTT, resource-constrained IoT devices can “publish” their sensor/actuator data to a central broker on a predetermined topic. The broker consequently distributes this information to subscribers of that topic [3]. Due to its functionality in unreliable network conditions, MQTT has been adopted in many fields like smart homes, industry, agriculture, etc. [4]. Despite such advantages, there are several security challenges that affect MQTT. First, MQTT networks tend to lack built-in security measures. For instance, although TLS encryption can be activated, by default, data is transmitted in plaintext. Also, MQTT clients and brokers are susceptible to DoS attacks and malformed packets injection that exploit protocol parser weaknesses that disrupt ongoing IoT services. Thus, facing these challenges requires solutions beyond traditional Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) that consider the specificity of MQTT as a protocol with its own traffic patterns [5].

With this in mind, we gather and analyze a collection of over 45M benign and 166M malicious raw packets from 6 different datasets, where we filter out any non-MQTT specific attacks. After converting these packets into traffic flows¹ – which we publicly share with the research community – using

NTLFlowLyzer, Argus and Zeek Flowmeter, we run the K-means clustering algorithm several times on each dataset to find the optimum number of clusters K based on K ’s highest Silhouette score [6]. In over 65% of the cases, optimum K (K) is 2 regardless of the number of attack types in the original dataset. Further analysis that we carry out using feature ranking shows that the weight of the feature **Flow Duration**’s ranges between 70% and 90% in all the datasets, thus explaining K ’s low value. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first covering MQTT traffic attacks using such a comparative analysis of 3 different tools at this scale.

Our work is organized as follows: Section II provides background and Section III covers the related work. Section IV explains the methodology. Section V shows the results of our experiments. Section VI discusses the results. Finally, Section VII concludes this paper and highlights future work.

II. BACKGROUND

First introduced in 1999, MQTT is the most significant IoT protocol. It is a publish-subscribe protocol that is efficient, lightweight, scalable, and highly functional in unreliable networks. This makes it ideal for IoT environments as it suits the resource-constrained nature of IoT devices. Based on a client-broker architecture, clients either publish or subscribe to the broker’s topics. The broker receives messages on given topics from the publishing client and forwards them to all those subscribed to them, allowing for indirect communication among the clients. Also, brokers can retain messages and support a feature known as the Last Will and Testament (LWT). This eases the impact of unexpected disconnections of any publishing client on other clients that are subscribed to its topics. MQTT has 3 Quality of Service (QoS) levels – 0 (at most once), 1 (at least once), and 2 (exactly once), which enables balancing performance and reliability based on network’s requirements. Besides, MQTT preserves stateful sessions by tracking client subscriptions and storing undelivered messages, a feature crucial for devices operating with intermittent network connectivity. Also, the protocol supports authentication using both credentials and certificates as well as secure communication using TLS/SSL. Thus, with all these features, MQTT stands out for being a reliable protocol for IoT communication across constrained networks [7] [8].

On the other hand, MQTT is vulnerable to several types of attacks. While some of the attacks are protocol specific, others are generic. The protocol specific ones include Malformed Packets attack which involves sending malformed packets that exploit the broker’s parser or implementation vulnerabilities. Another MQTT-specific attack is the SlowITe one, which is a

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¹traffic flows enable aggregated features like packet counts, durations, inter-arrival times, etc.

slow DoS attack that keeps many open connections with the broker by sending data slowly, ultimately rendering the broker unavailable for legitimate clients. Moreover, other protocol specific attacks include MQTT DoS attack which floods the broker with excessive CONNECT or PUBLISH messages, and Topic Hijacking in which unauthorized access to topics is obtained. For generic attacks, MQTT is vulnerable to any type of attack on TCP given that it is based on TCP e.g. SYN Flooding and TCP Reset [5], [9]–[12].

III. RELATED WORK

A. MQTT Security and Attacks

MQTT security has received increasing attention lately. As an application layer protocol, MQTT devices may suffer vulnerabilities that require certain countermeasures. Husnain et al. [13] analyzed the National Vulnerability Database and the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures for MQTT vulnerabilities and found 81 vulnerabilities between Apr. 2014 and Dec. 2021. They classified them into 3 main categories:

- *Required Fields Checks* (37 vulnerabilities): Because the required fields in MQTT packets depend on the packet type, improper validation, e.g. omitting password check when a username is supplied, was shown to cause server crashes, buffer overflows, and remote code execution.
- *Lack of Logical Errors Checks* (25): Missing logical error checks in MQTT networks can lead to crashes, buffer overflows, and DoS attacks when processing crafted packets. The reported vulnerabilities show exploits of fields like *Keep-Alive* and *Will Delay Interval*.
- *Improper Packet Length Checks* (12): Packet parsing helps identify packet fields. Yet, without proper length checks, attackers can exploit sequential parsing using crafted packets. This can cause remote code execution, buffer overflows, DoS, and unauthorized memory access.

Thus, Husnain et al. [13] propose an MQTT parsing engine that integrates with MQTT network-based IDS and runs extensive checks on traffic using rigorous validation of packet fields when parsing packets. The engine would implement these 5 steps: 1) *protocol intuition*, 2) *vulnerability assessment*, 3) *protocol identification*, 4) *parsing*, and 5) *strict validation*.

Hintaw et al. [14] studied MQTT's security challenges and solutions by analyzing security considerations at different layers of IoT systems that use MQTT. For the Physical layer, they considered that systems should be run on private networks. They suggested the use of point-to-point or peer-to-peer structure to control shared communication channels. For the Network layer, they proposed using IPSec for confidentiality and authentication but noted the limitation of extra headers. A solution to the limitation could be 6LoWPAN compression. An alternative approach would be the Host Identity Protocol [15] which separates node identifiers and brokers from their locators, although implementing public key distribution and cryptographic schemes would be a challenge. At the Transport layer, while implementing TLS would not be practical given the resource-constrained nature of the devices, using TLS Session Resumption can notably reduce repeated TLS Handshakes. Although costly in terms of hardware and power

consumption, an alternative involves using hardware-based TLS implementations. In all cases, whenever possible, the use of certificates and TLS are recommended in MQTT's specification [3]. Hintaw et al. highlight that although the use of TLS helps protect traffic, incorrect TLS configuration, e.g. vulnerable TLS versions used for compatibility reasons with legacy devices, would make the network exposed. Finally, for the application layer, *OAuth* or *LDAP*, which are external authentication systems, can be used for brokers. This external system would be in charge of enabling access to token and of credential-based authentication. Yet, there are complexities involved in implementing these systems such as latency.

Hintaw et al. consider these drawbacks of current security mechanisms: 1) *High Complexity* for the use of the suggested security mechanisms. This is evident resource consumption and processes execution. More complex mechanisms require more resources for operations like MQTT payload encryption-decryption. 2) *Partial Protection for MQTT Protocol*: Some approaches may solve complexity while introducing new vulnerabilities. For example, using a challenge-based shuffling algorithm at both client and server for key dynamic generation, a new security protocol proposes a fixed master key imprinted in devices. However, the dynamic session keys might remain exposed for a while, which enable attackers to decrypt communication. 3) *Additional Service Requirements*: When devices have sufficient resources, traditional encryption methods for MQTT traffic at the application layer are viable. However, these schemes are limited in the areas of key management scalability, fine-grain access control and flexible data sharing.

B. MQTT Intrusion and Malicious Traffic Detection Systems

Hindy et al. [5] note that traditional IDS struggle with IoT protocols like MQTT, essentially failing to distinguish between benign and malicious traffic, because of their limited visibility into IoT device behavior and focus on enterprise traffic patterns [5]. Thus, the authors propose a specialized IDS system for MQTT networks, which they test against their own built dataset, which features different MQTT attacks. They tested multiple ML models, after converting the traffic into flows. Their results showed that their flow-based approach can achieve higher detection rates vs. generic IDS. Sultan et al. [16] focused on MitM attack detection in MQTT networks using five different ML algorithms: *Artificial Neural Network (ANN)*, *Naïve Bayes (NB)*, *Decision Trees (DT)*, *K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)* and *eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB)*. Their accuracy was between 95.9% (KNN) and 99.6% for XGB and training time was between 0.008 seconds (KNN) and 8.49 seconds (ANN). The results show that while securing the network is critical trade-offs are sometimes needed, particularly in resources-constraint environment like MQTT networks.

Alzahrani and Aldhyani [17] studied traditional ML and Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches for MQTT intrusion detection. They tested several ML algorithms: *KNN* and *Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)*, and deep learning models: *Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)* and *CNN Long Short-Term Memory Networks (CNN-LSTM)* on an MQTT attacks set. They found that CNN-LSTM had the best accuracy (98%)

Fig. 1: Pipeline for Experiments

in identifying attacks vs. the other models (LDA: 76%, CNN: 80.3% and KNN: 80.8%). Although this suggests that complex non-linear models can capture subtle patterns in MQTT traffic, deep models have higher computational requirements, making their use impractical for constrained-resources networks.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section details the workflow that we designed to analyze raw MQTT network traffic (benign and malicious).

A. Dataset Collection

In our work, we sought an approach that would help us build an eye-bird view of existing MQTT attacks based on publicly available datasets. To this end, we carried out an exhaustive search of datasets that were addressed in the literature and that focused on MQTT attacks. While several datasets claim that they involve MQTT attacks, we believe that not all are. To put it in other words, we believe that, while some datasets involve attacks on MQTT networks, these attacks are not always on the application level – where MQTT sits. For this, our dataset collection process involved these phases:

- 1) Search within the literature of mentions of MQTT attack-based datasets.
- 2) Analysis of the descriptions of the datasets: we discarded those that involved attacks that were not on the MQTT protocol itself. If the dataset included mixed attack types, we discarded the ones that were not MQTT.

With this approach, we ended up selecting a collection of 6 datasets that included various attack scenarios as well as benign traffic (except for CICIoMT) as described in detail in Table I. Our final collection contains 45.2M benign raw packets and 166.35M malicious packets. The traffic of these attacks were either simulated using publicly available tools or using custom scripts developed by the authors.

B. Pipeline

Our pipeline is composed of these main stages:

- 1) Raw packets are converted into flow representations.
- 2) The data undergoes preprocessing, including cleansing, normalization, and feature selection.
- 3) K-means clustering is performed with and without PCA
- 4) Run feature ranking algorithm to find the most significant features (post-processing).

A visual representation of the pipeline is provided in Fig. 1.

C. Flow extraction

Once our initial pcaps set was selected, we extracted flows from them using Argus, NTLFlowLyzer and Zeek-Flowmeter (Zeek, hereafter). In some cases, the flow generation would be incomplete (due to errors/warning) for a certain tool, leading us to discard the processing of a given pcap using that specific tool. An example is the following message: “*Your trace file likely has invalid TCP checksums, most likely from NIC checksum offloading. By default, packets with invalid checksums are discarded by Zeek ...*”. In total, we successfully processed, using the 3 tools, 215 pcap files of which 197 belong to DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT dataset. Figure 2 shows the Probability Density Function (PDF) for the pairwise ratio between the flows generated by each tool: $\frac{Zeek}{Argus}, \frac{Argus}{NTLFlowLyzer}$ and $\frac{Zeek}{NTLFlowLyzer}$. The figure shows the flows’ densities of all the 215 files in Figure 2a and all the files after excluding the 197 of DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT dataset in Figure 2b.

When generating the flows using the 3 tools, we ensured that all the possible fields that any given tool can generate are exported. NTLFlowLyzer generates 348 fields, argus generates 84 and Zeek Flowmeter generates 79. We modified Zeek Flowmeter to add the source and destination ports to the fields making the total number 81. The sizes of the flows of the 215 files for which all the 3 tools were executed successfully are as follows: a) *Argus*: 6.02 GB, b) *NTLFlowLyzer*: 66.83 GB, c) *Zeek*: 6.95 GB. Generating the flows for each of Argus and Zeek took a few minutes (less than 10 for any of the pcaps), while NTLFlowLyzer required in some cases around 6 days like in the case of CICIoMT’s Connect Flood DDoS attack.

To ensure that our analysis is solely focused on MQTT traffic, we exclude flows whose source or destination is not port 1883. Also, we note that although Secure MQTT (MQTTS) traffic can be encrypted and transported on port 8883, its analysis is beyond the scope of this work. Thus, any MQTTS, if existent within the flows, was discarded as well. Our scripts and traffic flows are available here².

D. Preprocessing

To maximize efficiency and reduce noise, we preprocessed our final flow collection. This involved encoding columns where possible and dropping columns with unique values or those whose influence was irrelevant or redundant for our study e.g. fields referring to *Start Time, End Time, Sequence*, etc. Additionally, where adequate, we reduced the size of the values in the dataframes by converting *Int64* to *Int32* and *Float64* to *Float32*. Also, we merged the source and destination ports in 1 field that indicates the direction of the flow from or to port 1883. For NTLFlowLyzer, given the number of fields (348), we dropped statistical fields that we found to be additional to the original flow data. If no original data existed, we maintained the mean and standard deviation.

E. Clustering

We use clustering to analyze the datasets and similarities among their various traffic types. Our end goal is to identify

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Dataset	Yr	Traffic		Testbed	Domain	Attack	Packets	Tool	Benign Pkts.
		Sim.	Real						
Artemis [18]	19	Y	Y	N/A	-	Flooding: DoS	422K	MQTT-malaria	179K
						Flooding: DoS	130K		
MQTTset [19]	20	Y		10 sensors	Smart Home /Office	MQTT Publish Flood	613	MQTTSA	11M
						Brute-Force Authentication	14K		
						malformed data	10K		
						SlowITe	9.2K		
MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 [5]	20	Y		12 sensors/ sim. cam. feed	Smart Home	MQTT brute-force	10M	MQTT-PWN	1.07M
DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT [20]	23		Y	52 sensors	Industrial	CONNECT Flooding DoS	26.29M	custom script	32.46M
						CONNECT Flooding DDoS	24.6M		
						Delayed CONNECT Flooding DDoS	25.56M		
						Delayed CONNECT Flooding DoS	21.36M		
						Invalid Subscription Flooding DDoS	955K		
						Invalid Subscription Flooding DoS	920K		
						CONNECT Flooding with WILL Payload DDoS	15.56M		
						CONNECT Flooding with WILL Payload DoS	8.34M		
GothX - MQTTset Reproduction [21]	24	Y		10 sensors	-	Malformed data	1.09K	MQTTSA	494K
						SlowITe	31K		
						brute force authentication	21K		
						MQTT Publish Flood	7.29K		
						Flooding Denial of Service	90K		
CICIoMT2024 [10]	24	Y	Y	25 real + 15 sim. IoMT devices (MQTT is sim.)	HealthCare	Publish Flooding DDoS	3.59M	custom script	-
						Publish Flooding DoS	5.28M		
						Connect Flooding DDoS	21M		
						Connect Flooding DoS	1.59M		
						Malformed Data	68K		

TABLE I: Overview of MQTT-based IoT datasets and attack scenarios

(a) All files

(b) All except DoS/DDoS dataset files

Fig. 2: Probability Density Function with and without DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT files

existing patterns and characteristics of these traffic types. Our clustering experiments are run on each dataset separately.

We run our experiments for each of the 3 tools. Based on a preliminary analysis, we only use the K-means given its lightweight compared to other clustering algorithms. In the process, we tested both HDBscan and DBScan but were limited by our computational resources to process such a large collection of data across the tools. We test on various values of K and identify the best K value using the Silhouette score. In the literature, Silhouette scores are used to measure the quality of clusters. Ranging between -1 and 1, the higher the value, the more coherent the cluster. This ranges from -1 indicating that the sample is in the wrong cluster to 1 meaning that it is in the correct one. The Silhouette score is the mean of all the Silhouette coefficients in the dataset. For each sample, the coefficient is calculated by considering, both the mean intra-cluster distance a and the mean nearest-cluster distance b . The following equation is used [6]:

$$(b - a) / \max(a, b) \tag{1}$$

After testing this approach, Shahapure and Nicholas [6] consider an adequate one to find “a good value” for K.

Also, we run our clustering tests with and without dimensionality reduction, using PCA, to see its influences on output clusters. Our experiments test over the same range of K values while also varying the number of components of PCA.

(a) Artemis

(b) CICIoMT

(c) GothX

(d) MQTTset Original

Fig. 3: Zeek clusters. Left to right and top to bottom: 1) no PCA, 2) no. comp=10, 3) no. comp=20, 4) no. comp=30.

Fig. 4: Zeek clusters of DoS-DDoS-MQTT-IoT (left) and MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 (right) without dimensionality reduction

(a) Artemis

(b) GothX

(c) MQTTset

Fig. 5: Clusters of NTLFlowlyzer flows with and without dimensionality reduction applied.

Fig. 6: NTLFlowLyzer clusters for CICIoMT (left) and MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 (right) without dimensionality reduction

F. Post-Clustering Analysis

To understand the basis of the boundaries between the clusters, we run more experiments that involve feature ranking. For this objective, we preliminarily tested 3 candidate algorithms: *Mutual Information (MI)*, *Laplacian Score* and *PCA*. Our tests showed that PCA yielded the best results that indicated the feature weights, while MI led to lesser significant feature rankings. Laplacian’s results were almost 0 in all of our tests.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we highlight the results of our clustering experiments on individual datasets of the generated flows by the 3 tools. Using the K-means clustering algorithm.

A. Zeek

For datasets *Artemis*, *GothX*, *MQTTset* and *CICIoMT*, we tested K-means in the range $K=2,3,4,\dots,16$. We repeated this after applying PCA with *No. components=10, 20, 30*. The results, shown in Figure 3, provide an overview of the optimum number of clusters, based on the best Silhouette Score in the K range of [2-16]. For Artemis, CICIoMT and MQTTset, $K=2$ with and without PCA. Regarding GothX, $K=3$ for all the cases except for PCA with No. components=10, where the $K=14$. On the other hand, Figure 4 shows the num. clusters from DoS-DDoS-MQTT-IoT and MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 sets without dimensionality reduction. $K=16$ and 2 respectively.

B. NTLFlowLyzer

Similar to the method used in Section V-A, we do the same experiments using NTLFlowLyzer excluding CICIoMT due to computation limitations. The results, shown in Figure 5, show that Artemis is optimum at $K=2$ for all the cases. For GothX, for both the non-PCA case and PCA with 30 components case, $K=16$, for PCA with 10 and 20 components $K=12$ and 13 consecutively. For MQTTset, K for non-PCA and PCA 20 is 16, for PCA 10 and PCA 30, $K= 2$ and 15 consecutively.

C. Argus

With the same experiments for Argus, the results are shown in Figure 7. K for Artemis is 15 for all except PCA 10 for which $K=14$. For GothX, MQTTset and CICIoMT, $K=2$ for all the cases. We highlight that MQTTset has only PCA 10 and 20 as its feature set is less than 30 already. Thus, it is not possible to perform PCA 30 given that the dimensionality of the feature set is already less than 30. On the other hand, Figure 8 shows num_clusters for non-reduced DoS-DDoS-MQTT-IoT and MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 argus flows, with $K=2$ in both cases.

Fig. 7: Clusters for argus flows across 4 datasets with and without dimensionality reduction applied.

Fig. 8: Argus flow results for DoS-DDoS-MQTT-IoT (left) and MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 (right) without dimensionality reduction

D. Post-processing Feature Ranking

With the aim of understanding the nature of the clusters as shown in the figures above, where boundaries are overlapping in many cases, we study the feature rankings of the generated flow files. As highlighted in Section IV-F, we rely on both PCA and MI to identify the top influencing features in clustering.

For PCA, as demonstrated in Figure 9, for all the flows that we generated, the top feature was the Duration field titled (flow_duration in Zeek, duration in NTLFlowLyzer and Dur in argus). While the following most significant feature was fwd_pkts_count in Zeek and packets in NTLFlowLyzer, it was Runtime in argus. However, the top features were the same for all the files with the Duration field being almost 1 in many cases. For MI ranking, the top features varied across the flows. However, the weights were much less significant with the most significant feature for the output flows of the 3 tools being less than **0.5** and in only 4 flows having a value higher than **0.1**.

Fig. 9: PCA Top Features Boxplot: Zeek and NTLFlowLyzer (top row left to right) and Argus (bottom row)

VI. DISCUSSION

Given the exploratory nature of this work, we discuss the results that we obtained from our experiments in this sense. The unsupervised approach is one that is more representative of the real-world for the traffic analysis context. Thanks to the controlled environment of the traffic generation in the different testbeds, we have ground truth for the datasets that we studied. We discuss the results in different aspects next.

A. Clustering Performance and Optimality

After viewing the results for the various experiments that we ran in Sections V-A, V-B and V-C, we recognize that the value of K , which indicates the number of cluster, does not follow the same distribution of attacks within the datasets. For instance, CICIOMT’s K for Zeek, Argus and NTLFlowLyzer flows is 2 regardless of whether PCA is applied or not, while the original number of classes/attacks is 4. Additionally, we were unable to find a clear impact on the use of PCA with 10, 20 and 30 components although it caused changes in K in some cases. For instance, it did not have any impact on MQTTset’s no. of clusters for Zeek flows or Argus flows, while its impact could be seen for MQTTset’s NTLFlowLyzer flows. Even in this case, the number of clusters then varied between 16 without PCA and 2, 16 and 15 for the no. of components 10, 20 and 30 respectively. Another observation is that in 32 of the 49 K ’s we obtained, K was equivalent to 2 as shown in Figures 3, 5 and 7 (representing 65% of the cases). This in itself indicates a great similarity among the samples of the different original classes.

With regards to the results in Section V-D, the fact that a single feature has most of the weight of the top features when using the PCA feature ranking approach explains the overlapping boundaries in some plots. It also explains why in many cases a low value of K is the most K compared to the number of original classes/attacks. We believe that with the flow duration weight ranging between 0.5 and 1 and the median between 0.7 and 0.9 for Zeek, NTLFlowLyzer and Argus flows, it becomes more difficult to separate the clusters in the same number of attacks provided in the datasets despite our MQTT-focused approach. Hence, traditional IDS tools are not adequate for detecting different MQTT attack types.

B. Tools

With NTLFlowLyzer generating a massive number of features compared to Argus and Zeek, we consider this to be one of the reasons behind the tool’s flows’ output size. Another reason is that NTLFlowLyzer in some cases has generated enormous numbers of flows per file compared to Argus and Zeek. For instance, in CICIOMT’s DDoS-Publish Flood attack, the number of flows for Argus and Zeek were 58K and 50K consecutively, while it was over 748K for NTLFlowLyzer (13 times those of Argus and 15 times those of Zeek). Also, we highlight that Artemis – which has 2 different classes – clustering has its $K=2$ for Argus and Zeek. However, K for NTLFlowLyzer varies between 14 and 15; a phenomenon that is worth deeper analysis to understand how flows differ from each other based on the tool used.

C. Limitations

Our study suffered from several limitations. First, for NTLFlowLyzer, the flow generation required notably more time compared to the Zeek and Argus. Any scalable traffic classification/attack detection approach based on flows would not be compatible with NTLFlowLyzer unlike Argus and Zeek which need negligible execution time for flow generation.

Another limitation is related to the tools' inner designs. In our experiments, we treated the tools as black-boxes that generate flows from raw traffic. Any limitation within the flow generation design of the tools would be propagated in our results. Also, processing all the datasets collectively requires extremely powerful computational resources to be executed in reasonable time. The computational resources also limited our ability to apply different clustering techniques. Moreover, the datasets have imbalances between the attack types, which require adequate measures that avoid the negative influence of such imbalances. In this context, we highlight that traffic flows are mostly benign [22], indicating that any real-world solution would need to take this imbalance into account. Finally, while we tried our best to avoid such influence, some features might be redundant or might introduce noise in our design.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we carried out an exploratory study of several MQTT traffic datasets that included both attack and normal traffic datasets. Our goal was to understand the nature of the traffic and how the different types of attacks are classified. For this, we converted the raw traffic into traffic flows using 3 tools: Argus, Zeek Flowmeter and NTLFlowLyzer. Then, using the K-means clustering algorithms, we ran a series of experiments with and without dimensionality reduction to identify the optimum number of clusters for the different datasets, where we tested for different values of K (2-16). In 65% of the cases, the clusters had the K - based on the Silhouette score – equal to 2, indicating that the optimum number of clusters is 2. Thus, using feature ranking to identify the most important features and their weight, we found that flow duration was the most significant with a median between 0.7 and 0.9 for the flows generated by the 3 tool. With such a high weight, separating the cluster becomes a challenge, requiring for other innovative approaches.

Given our findings, we plan to further analyze the features of the different flows and attacks that allow for creating better boundaries between the clusters that reflect the differences between the attacks. Also, we will study the normal and attack traffic generation methods of the different attack tools discussed in Table I to understand their hidden influence on classifying different types of traffic (attack and benign). Finally, we aim to test other clustering algorithms like HDBScan.

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